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Are bold-shy personalities of European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) linked to stress tolerance and immunity? A scope of harnessing fish behavior in aquaculture

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ABSTRACT

The sensitivity to stress and its impact on immunity are supposedly related to a fish's personality. In the present study, European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) were exposed to an open-field and a novel-object test to identify distinctive shy and bold individuals. This series of cognitive tests revealed clear differences between proactive individuals with pronounced exploration behavior (bold personality) and reactive individuals that took a freeze-hide position (shy personality). A cohort of shy and bold perch was then exposed to elevated stocking density. Frozen activity and lower explorative behavior were related to higher basal and stocking-induced cortisol levels compared to proactive individuals. Since cortisol is a well-known modulator of immune-gene expression, we used multiplex real-time PCR to profile the differential immune responses to the intraperitoneal injection of *Aeromonas hydrophila* in the head kidney and peritoneal cells of bold and shy perch individuals. These expression differences between stimulated bold and shy perch were generally modest, except for the genes encoding the complement component c3 and the matrix metalloproteinase mmp9. The strong differential expression of these two bactericidal and inflammatory genes in the context of the modestly regulated features suggests that a fish's personality is linked to a particular immune-defense strategy. In conclusion, our approach, based on behavioral video observations, phagocytosis and enzyme assays, immunogene-expression profiling, and quantification of stress-relevant metabolites, revealed indications for divergent coping styles in cohorts of bold or shy European perch. This divergence could be exploited in future selective breeding programs.

1. Introduction

The European perch, *Perca fluviatilis*, is considered a suitable candidate for the diversification of European intensive aquaculture [1]. Its high market value, along with the increasing consumer demand, makes this species commercially important in European countries, where over 900 tons are produced annually [2]. Nowadays, European perch production relies heavily on intensive farming systems, i.e., recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS). Although rearing in RAS allows the improvement of some desirable traits, such as higher growth rate, greater survival, and adequate swim bladder inflation, the production of

European perch still fails to meet market demands. One bottleneck is the European perch's high sensitivity to distress conditions under captive conditions, as this reduces immune resistance while also increasing sensitivity to pathogens [3]. Pathogens are especially reported to impair growth and induce mass mortality [4]. To improve the biological efficiency of fish production, including enhanced disease resistance and robustness in intensively cultured species, selective breeding programs have been successfully applied for some fish species, such as Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) [5]. Identifying beneficial fish personalities and stress-coping strategies could therefore represent a promising target for selective perch breeding

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programs [6].

A major axis in the study of personalities (also referred to as “temperament” [7]) is the bold-shy continuum or degree of boldness [8]. Within or between populations, individuals exhibit consistent differences in their degree of exploration and risk-taking behavior. Bold-shy behavior is reported to be directly correlated with the degree of aggressiveness, foraging behavior, reaction to stress, and recovery time [9–11]. In the context of animal behavior research, the term “boldness” is often used to describe a certain degree of fearlessness and the willingness to take risks in novel or uncertain situations [12]. This boldness may increase the chances of discovering new resources or mates while avoiding competition with other individuals. However, boldness can also increase the risk of predation or injury and influence the general susceptibility and the dynamics of immune responses [13]. The term “shyness” refers to animals that are either naturally more timid than others or that display shy behavior in response to specific environmental cues or previous experiences. Shyness may increase the chances of avoiding potential threats and reducing the risk of injury or predation, but it can also limit an individual’s access to resources or mates, thereby reinforcing competitive behavior [12].

While shy animals display a more reclusive and reactive behavior when faced with an unfamiliar situation, bold individuals explore novel environments in a proactive manner. In addition, bold individuals behave in a relatively aggressive manner compared to shy ones, have higher social rank, spend more time in open spaces, have a faster recovery period from fear stimulation, and generally have an increased feed intake [14,15]. Notably, personality could be potentially heritable and transferred to the offspring [16]. Research on farmed fish has also documented the role of proactive/bold or reactive/shy personalities in behavior variation ([17], and references therein). This knowledge could be used to safeguard the sustainable development of the aquaculture industry.

The links between fish personality, metabolic performance, and stress responses have previously been studied in fish, but to our knowledge, the relationship between personality and immune competence has not yet been empirically demonstrated in fish. The distinction between proactive/bold and reactive/shy individuals and the selection of beneficial personalities could be useful if integrated into the breeding of European perch stocks to improve management as well as fish stocks to overcome current bottlenecks in European perch aquaculture and pave the way to economic growth. The aim of this study was to provide evidence of causal links between the bold personality of European perch and defense against pathogenic bacteria of the *Aeromonas* genus *in vivo*. We hypothesized that (a) bold individuals, when compared with shy individuals, would exhibit a lower stress response and faster recovery time after exposure to distress, and (b) the divergence in the bold and shy temperament would be reflected by distinct immune-gene expression profiles after stimulation of distress.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Fish acquisition and husbandry

A stock of 1000 juvenile European perch with a start weight of 20 ± 10 g was obtained from the FTN Aquaart AG Swiss commercial RAS farm. The fish were transported in late May 2022 in oxygenated polyethylene bags (filled 1/3 with water and 2/3 with oxygen) placed in thermoboxes and delivered to the RAS of the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia (Czech Republic).

After gradual water temperature acclimatization (1 °C per hour), each fish was tagged with a 7.0 × 1.4 mm pit tag (Loligo Systems ApS, Denmark) for subsequent individual detection and stocked in a separate white tank (net water volume 800 L) with a water exchange rate of 1.5 tanks per hour at a density of two individuals per L set within the same RAS. The concentration of oxygen (O₂ ≥ 90%), pH level (pH 7 ± 0.5), and temperature (20 °C ± 1 °C) were monitored twice daily throughout

the whole experiment with a HQ40D multimeter (Hach Lange, Germany). Concentrations of ammonium and nitrites were measured every second day with a portable spectrophotometer (DR 2800; Hach Company, USA). The light intensity was set at 250–300 lx at the water surface (DT-8809; Cem, China), and the photoperiod was constant at 12L:12D. To minimize stress, each stock was fed commercial pellets that had been obtained together with the fish from the abovementioned farm. The fish were fed by automatic fish feeders (TWINfeeder model 2582; Eheim, Germany) three times a day, at 7:30 a.m., 2:00 p.m., and 7:15 p.m., *ad libitum*. The fish were adapted to rearing conditions for two weeks before initiating the experiment.

2.2. Assessing fish personality in European perch stock

The personalities of European perch were assessed by subjecting 900 individuals to (a) an open-field test and (b) a novel-object test (Fig. 1).

a) Open-field test

Fish were gently netted from their rearing tanks and transferred to white rectangular tanks (one fish per tank; 37.0 cm [H] × 57.5 cm [W] × 73.5 cm [L]) filled with dechlorinated, aged tap water with the same water parameters as in the house rearing tanks and left for a 15 min acclimatization [18]. Each individual’s activity, defined as the distance moved during the 10 min test, was video recorded (camera type DS-2CD2043G0-I; Hikvision, China) for 10 min after acclimatization.

b) Novel-object test

The novel-object test was initiated immediately after the open-field test. A small yellow Lego block (LEGO 6176 DUPLO Basic Brick; LEGO, Denmark) representing the novel object was placed in the center of the tank, and the behavior of each fish was recorded for 30 min. Three parameters were determined from the video recordings, (a) the number of fish approaches to the Lego block, (b) the closest distance of the fish from the Lego block (zone A ≤ 5 cm, zone B ≤ 10 cm, zone C ≤ 15 cm, zone D ≤ 20 cm), and (c) the latency of the closest approach to the Lego block according to previous protocols [19,20]. The water in the experimental tanks was replaced between every single fish test.

The top 20 most proactive individuals (bold individuals [BI]) and the top 20 most reactive individuals (shy individuals [SI]) were stocked in new RAS tanks to assess and compare their stress and immune responses.

2.3. Crowding-challenge test

To induce a response to crowding, we decreased the water level in tanks in which bold individuals (BI) and shy individuals (SI) were stocked to 5 cm above the dorsal fins of the fish. After 30 min, the water volume was increased again to the original water level. Blood samples were collected from the caudal blood vessels of anesthetized fish (MS-222; 200 µg in 10 L water) using heparinized 1 mL Omnifix-F Solo syringes (Braun, Germany). Five individuals from the BI group and 5 individuals from the SI group were sampled at the following four time points: before decrease of the water level (control, CTRL) and at 30 min, 12 h, and 24 h after the water level returned to the original level. The blood samples were kept in reaction tubes (Eppendorf, Germany) on ice for less than 20 min before centrifugation (10,000×g, 10 min at 5 °C) to separate the plasma. The plasma samples were stored at –80 °C for further analyses. Blood physiological parameters, including the activities of alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and the concentrations of glucose and monovalent potassium ions (K⁺) were assessed using an Abbott Architect c8000 clinical chemistry analyzer and assay kits (Abbot Diagnostics, USA). The cortisol concentration was analyzed using a reagent kit and an automated immune analyzer (Immulite 2000 XPi; Siemens Healthineers, Germany). After

Fig. 1. Experimental design.

finishing the crowding-challenge test, the fish were left for seven recovery days.

2.4. Assessing potentially different immune responses between bold and shy personalities to *Aeromonas hydrophila* stimulation

A 100 μL suspension containing 5×10^7 inactivated *A. hydrophila* was injected into the peritoneal cavity of 30 European perch from the BI and SI groups (n = 15 per group). Another 6 individuals (n = 3 per group) were injected with 100 μL of sterile PBS to serve as negative controls. All fish were euthanized with an overdose of clove oil (0.6 mL/L) [21] and the head kidney and peritoneal leukocytes from 5 injected

fish per group were sampled at 1 d, 3 d, and 7 d post-injection. The head kidney and peritoneal leukocytes of the control fish were sampled at 7 d post-injection. The samples were stored in 700 μL RLT buffer (Qiagen, Germany) until RNA extraction.

2.5. Somatic indices

The calculation of somatic indices, including the hepatosomatic index (HSI), gonadosomatic index (GSI), perivisceralascular fat index (PVSI), spleenosomatic index (SSI), and cardiosomatic index (CSI), was used to estimate individual fish fitness. Somatic indices were calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{HSI} = \frac{100 \times \text{liver weight}}{\text{body weight (BW)}}$$

$$\text{GSI} = \frac{100 \times \text{gonad weight}}{\text{BW}}$$

$$\text{PVSII} = \frac{100 \times \text{fat weight}}{\text{BW}}$$

$$\text{SSI} = \frac{100 \times \text{spleen weight}}{\text{BW}}$$

$$\text{CSI} = \frac{100 \times \text{heart weight}}{\text{BW}}$$

The above indices were evaluated on 20 selected individuals per group (n = 40 in total) after euthanasia.

2.6. RNA extraction and multiplex quantitative PCR

A panel of assays specific for 46 immune-relevant genes was established using the Pyrosequencing Assay Design software (version 1.0.6; Biotage, Sweden) (Table 1). The primer-pair assays of the target genes and the reference genes *actb* and *rna18s* were tested before measurement to validate the proper amplification of target-gene fragments using the LightCycler 96 System (Roche, Germany) together with the SensiFAST SYBR No-ROX Kit (Bioline/Meridian Bioscience). Melting-curve analyses and agarose-gel electrophoresis validated the amplification of specific PCR products with the targeted length (see Table 1).

The total RNA from the head kidneys (n = 5 per group) was extracted using 1 mL TRIzol Reagent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) and subsequently purified with the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen, Germany). To isolate the total RNA from peritoneal cells, we used the ISOLATE II RNA Micro Kit (Bioline/Meridian Bioscience, Germany). Residual DNA was digested using RNase-free DNase I (Qiagen) for 12 min at 37 °C. The concentration and the purity of the extracted RNA were assessed using a NanoDrop OneC spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, USA). The total RNA was adjusted to a concentration of 10 ng/μL and reverse-transcribed (42 °C, 30 min) using the Reverse Transcription Master Mix (Standard BioTools, USA). The resulting cDNA aliquots were mixed with the above-mentioned primer pairs (100 μM) and the PreAmp master mix (Standard BioTools) and individually pre-amplified in 13 cycles (95 °C, 15 s; 60 °C, 4 min) in a TAdvanced thermocycler (Analytik Jena, Germany). After this pre-amplification step, exonuclease I (New England Biolabs, Germany) was added to degrade the single-stranded oligonucleotide primers. After a 30 min incubation period at 37 °C, 43 μL TE buffer (Sigma-Aldrich/Merck, Germany) was added per sample. The multiplex quantitative PCR (qPCR) analyses were performed on two 48.48 Gene Expression biochips (Standard BioTools) using the BioMark HD system (Standard BioTools). First, each of the above 50 μL cDNA samples was diluted in SsoFast EvaGreen Supermix with Low ROX (Bio-Rad, Germany) and 20 × DNA Binding Dye Sample Loading Reagent (Standard BioTools) to produce the sample mixes. After priming the 48.48 biochips in the MX Controller (Standard BioTools), the primers and the sample mixes, together with one no-template (water) control, were transferred to the assay and sample inlets on the two primed 48.48 biochips. Finally, multiplex qPCR was conducted following the manufacturer's thermal protocol 'GE Fast 48.48 PCR + Melt v2.pcl'.

2.7. Phagocytosis of latex beads

To evaluate the phagocytic potential of the head-kidney leucocytes from the BI and SI injected with *A. hydrophila* or PBS, the head kidneys from 3 individuals per group (weight of each fish = 50.67 ± 2.29 g) were homogenized and immediately diluted in 3 mL of cold RPMI-1640 medium (P-Lab, cat. no. R.9085.1; Czech Republic) to prepare single-cell suspensions, as previously described [22]. The cell suspensions were

layered onto an isotonic Percoll gradient (r = 1.075 g/mL, Sigma-Aldrich/Merck cat.no. GE17-0891-01) and centrifuged at 1500×g for 30 min. Cells at the Percoll/RPMI-1640 medium interphase were collected and washed twice with 10 mL of RPMI-1640 medium. The final concentration of 5 × 10⁶ cells/mL was resuspended in 199.75 μL RPMI-1640 medium and mixed with 0.25 μL latex beads (cat. no L4655-1 ML; Sigma-Aldrich/Merck). Head-kidney leucocytes were incubated at 20 °C for 2 h. Following incubation, the cells were measured on a BD FACSCanto II instrument (BD, USA) and gated by forward and size scatter. FITC-positive cells were considered phagocytic cells and their proportion was calculated relative to the total number of acquired leucocytes.

2.8. Data analysis

All videos (from the open-field test and novel-object test) were processed semiautomatically with MATLAB software (MathWorks Inc., USA), using an in-house image-processing script implemented in MATLAB to detect the centroid of the fish. The distance that each fish swam was calculated based on the fish centroid and the frame rate of the camera. In the videos from the novel-object test, the region of the image that was out of the water was manually labeled by the image mask. A fish was detected as the largest object after edge detection in the mask. The Lego block was detected as a yellow object by thresholding the image by color. The distance between the fish and Lego block was calculated by finding the smallest distance between the objects' edges in pixels (1 pixel = 0.0264583333 cm). The pixel distance value was then converted to centimeters. The pixel size was previously calculated from the known box size. The time of the closest approach was calculated from the camera frame rate (e.g., 29.97 frames per second) [20].

The novel-object and open-field test parameters, blood plasma indices, somatic indices, and phagocytic capacity parameters did not meet the assumption of the parametric test (MANOVA, ANOVA) and were therefore analyzed using the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis H test with multiple comparisons of means as a post-hoc test.

The multiplex qPCR data were analyzed using the RealTime PCR Analysis Software v. 4.5.2 (Standard BioTools) and normalized against the suitable reference gene *actb*. The normalized copy numbers of the target genes were then evaluated using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA; GraphPad PRISM, software 9.5.1, GraphPad Software Inc., USA), with significance levels given as p-values. For identification of differentially expressed genes between BI versus SI, Holm-Šidák's multiple comparisons tests (GraphPad PRISM, software 9.5.1) were applied to control the familywise error rate (the adjusted p-values are termed q-values in the following). The list of differentially expressed genes was used for a functional upstream analysis with the Ingenuity program (Ingenuity Pathway Analyses, Ingenuity Systems/Qiagen). Benjamini-Hochberg multiple testing was performed and p < 0.05 was considered to be the cut-off score.

3. Results

3.1. Identification of bold and shy individuals in a European perch stock

In two test situations ("open field" and "novel object"), we selected the top 20 most proactive/bold individuals (BI, with the highest scores in both tests; Table 2) and the top 20 most reactive/shy individuals (SI, with a score of zero in both tests; Table 2) for a subsequent evaluation of their stress and immune responses.

3.2. Assessment of the stress-resistance capacity of bold and shy personalities

The crowding challenge (induced by lowering the water level for 30 min) had only a minor impact on the plasma parameters investigated in the selected bold and shy individuals (Table 3). The levels of glucose,

Table 1
Gene-specific qPCR primers used in this study.

Gene symbol	Gene product	Selected functions	Site of expression (in mammals)	Sense primer, antisense primer (5'→3')	NCBI gene ID	Fragment length (bp)
Reference genes:						
<i>rna18s</i>	18S ribosomal RNA	Structure of eukaryotic ribosomes	Ubiquitous expression	GTCGCCTGAATACCGCAGCTA, GTGAAATCTTGGACCGGCGC	114551681	144
<i>actb</i>	Actin-beta	Cell structure and motility, intercellular signaling	Ubiquitous expression	AGACATCAGGGTGTGATGGTTG, AGTACCCCATTTGAGCACGGTAT	114568982	110
Cytokines:						
<i>ccl20</i>	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 20	Chemotaxis of lymphocytes and also neutrophils	Neutrophils, enterocytes, B cells and dendritic cells	CATCTGCAGTGCGCCATGGAT, CCCTCTTTGTGTGGAAAATGATG	114565790	135
<i>ccl25</i>	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 25	Development of T-cells; chemotaxis of thymocytes, macrophages, and dendritic cells	Dendritic cells, epithelial cells and cells of small intestine	AGTCTTGACACAAGGCTCGTTTG, GGAAACAGATGGGGATTGCAAC	114561273	96
<i>cxcl8</i>	Interleukin-8	Chemotaxis of granulocytes; stimulation of phagocytosis and respiratory burst; angiogenesis	Macrophages and other cell types such as epithelial cells, airway smooth muscle cells and endothelial cells	GATGATCCCTGAGGGTATTCTG, GATTTGTCTGGACCCTGATGCT	114570874	193
<i>ifng</i>	Interferon-gamma	Antiviral defense incl. activation of macrophages	NK cells and cytotoxic T cells; also non-cytotoxic innate lymphoid cells	GCAGCACTATACTATCCCAATTAA, TGATCGGCCAGATGTTGAAGCA	114550360	150
<i>il1b</i>	Interleukin-1 beta	Inflammatory response	Activated macrophages, monocytes, fibroblasts and dendritic cells; also B cells, NK cells, epithelial cells	CTTGAGGTTGTGGAGCGACAG, ATGTCTGTGCCTTCCCAACT	114555628	127
<i>il6</i>	Interleukin-6	Proinflammatory and inflammatory responses	Monocytes, endothelial cells, and adipose tissue	AACTTCAGCAAGGAGGCTTGTG, CGCCGTAGTATCGAACTCTT	114555836	127
<i>il10</i>	Interleukin-10	Downregulation of Th1 responses; promotion of B cell survival, proliferation, and antibody production	Monocytes, lymphocytes	GACTTCTATGAAGCCAACGATGA, TACTGGAGTTTATCTGAGCACG	114554280	123
<i>il12b</i>	Interleukin-12B	Induction of Th1-cell development	Activated macrophages	GATAATGTTCTGGTCTGAGAGT, GTGGTTTGAAGAAAACGGTAAT	114566315	110
<i>il15</i>	Interleukin-15	Activation and proliferation of T and NK cells; NK cell development	Mononuclear phagocytes	CGCCATTGAGAAATCTGATGCTA, GGAGTTGTTGGTGGTCAATCATG	114565487	109
<i>il17a</i>	Interleukin-17α	Proinflammatory response	T cells	ATGCTGTGGGTTTGAAGGCTT, CCTCACCGTCTGGCCCTTCA	114556808	126
<i>il17f</i>	Interleukin-17F	Inflammatory and allergic responses	T helper 17 cells	CGTGGACGTACAGAGACTCCT, CTGGAGGCCAAACCTATCTACT	114573652	135
<i>il4i1</i>	Interleukin 4- induced protein 1, alias l-amino acid oxidase	Regulation of M2 macrophages; polarization and Th1-cell-induced inflammation; antibacterial function	B cells, macrophages, dendritic cells	CAAACCTCTTCTCTGGTTCTA, ACTACAGCGAGCTTCTCGACAT	114552578	114
<i>tnf</i>	Tumor necrosis factor alpha	Cell survival, proliferation, differentiation, and death; inflammation	Immune cells including macrophages, natural killer cells, and lymphocytes	CCATTCATTTAGAAGGAGACTACA, CAAGGAGGGCTAGAATCAACA	114568210	102
Acute-phase proteins:						
<i>c3</i>	Complement component 3	Activation of the complement pathway; opsonization	Hepatocytes, myeloid cells	GCTCCATTGAAGGTGATGCTGT, ACTTCCAGGAGCTCGGACAAAT	114566147	200
<i>hp</i>	Haptoglobin	Binding of free plasma hemoglobin; antioxidant; antibacterial activity; acute phase response	Hepatocytes; cells of skin, lung and kidney	CTCTGTGTCAGCCTCCAGGTT, CATGGTCTACATCGCTGACAGT	114558363	106
<i>saa5</i>	Serum amyloid A protein 5	Transport of cholesterol; recruitment of immune cells to inflammatory sites; induction of enzymes to degrade extracellular matrix	Hepatocytes, adipocytes	TGAAGCCTTCAAGGAGCTGGT, GAGGTATCAGTAATGCCAGAGA	114559349	165
<i>serping1</i>	Serpin family G member 1	Regulation of the classical complement pathway and blood coagulation	Hepatocytes	AGTTGATGCATCCATTAGCTATAC, GTTCAAAGAGACGGGTCCTAAC	114569644	127
Cell population markers:						
<i>tgfbr</i>	Transforming growth factor β receptor	Promotion of regulatory T-cell differentiation	Plasmacytoid dendritic cells and other immune cells	CATACCGCCCTCAGTGTITAC, TAAGTCGGGGCGCCAGCTGA	114549045	103
<i>cd4</i>	Cluster of differentiation 4	Communication with antigen-presenting cells	T-helper cells	AGGGGCACAAGAGTTGATATATTA, GCAAGTTCTATTTCACCAAAGTAC	120561820	114
<i>cd8a</i>	Cluster of differentiation 8, isoform A	Communication with antigen-presenting cells	Cytotoxic T cells	GACTGGTCGGAGAAAAAGCTGA, TTTCCCCTTGCTCGTTAATGTTG	120556913	123

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Gene symbol	Gene product	Selected functions	Site of expression (in mammals)	Sense primer, antisense primer (5'→3')	NCBI gene ID	Fragment length (bp)
<i>cd8b</i>	cluster of differentiation 8, isoform B	Communication with antigen-presenting cells	Cytotoxic T cells	TGCAGCCTCAGCTGGATCTCT, TTGCTATCAGACCCGTACATAGA	120573547	170
<i>tlr2</i>	Toll-like receptor 2	Detection of pathogen-associated molecular patterns	Immune cells including macrophages and granulocytes	ACTCTGGAAAGAACTGGATCTA, AAGCTACATTTGTCTAATAACCCGC	114562422	92
<i>cd68</i>	Cluster of differentiation 68	Promotion of phagocytosis, recruitment, and activation of macrophages	Monocytes/macrophages	CTGGTGTCTCAGCACTGTCA, CACGAAAACCACCCCCAAACC	114545695	128
<i>cd209</i>	Cluster of differentiation 209	Cell adhesion and pathogen recognition	Monocytes/macrophages	ACACGGAGAGACCAGACACT, TCTGTCTGGCAGTGTCTGTCT	120570942	91
<i>itga2</i> (alias <i>cd49b</i>)	Integrin alpha-2	Adhesion of platelets and other cells to collagens	T cells, NK cells, fibroblasts, platelets	AAGAGGAAAACAGATCGGGTCA, TCTCTCAGATCGCTCATGAACA	120561232	121
<i>cd74</i> (alias <i>mhc</i> , class II invariant chain)	Cluster of differentiation 74 or major histocompatibility complex, class II invariant chain α	Intracellular sorting of MHC class II molecules	B cells, T-cells, macrophages, activated endothelial cells, and neoplastic plasma cells	GGACCCACAGGGGGCTCTAA, GATCTGCTCCTTCTGGTCAAAC	120567310	123
<i>klrd1</i> (alias <i>cd94</i>)	Killer cell lectin like receptor D1	Regulation of NK cell function	NK cells	ACCTCAATCATTACTCCCAACAT, AGATGACTGTCAGCAAAGAGGC		114
<i>ighm</i>	Immunoglobulin isotype μ , heavy chain	Opsonization and complement activation; neutralization of toxins	B cells, especially plasma B cells	TCTGCTGGCAGGTGTGATG, ACTGGATGGCCTGGATCAGAC	114569330	135
<i>timd4</i>	T cell immunoglobulin and mucin domain containing 4	Phosphatidylserine binding activity during apoptosis	T cells	GCTCTCTCACAGTCAGTGAAT, TGCAGCCTGAGTTGGTATTTGT	120543985	148
<i>il2rb</i> (alias <i>cd122</i>)	Interleukin-2 receptor beta chain	Proliferation of cytotoxic T cells	Lymphocytes	TGCAGGACTCTCTGCGTA, GGACTGCTGGATCGTTGGTGT	114570378	101
<i>il6ra</i>	Interleukin-6 receptor-alpha	Inflammatory response, regulation of cell growth and differentiation	Monocytes, lymphocytes, fibroblasts, endothelial cells	AGAAAAGACCCTCCCCTGGT, GTCTGGCAATGCTGACCTTAC	114557568	109
<i>il6rb</i>	Interleukin-6 receptor-beta	Inflammatory response, regulation of cell growth and differentiation	Monocytes, lymphocytes, fibroblasts, endothelial cells	CTCATCTTCAGCAGCGGAGATA, CTCCCTCCCCATCATGTAGTTT	114555836	108
<i>il7r</i>	Interleukin-7 receptor	Survival, proliferation, and development of T cells	Naïve thymocytes and memory T cells	CGACACAGAGCCAGAAATCCT, GCAACAACGAGGACGACGAAG	114570789	104
<i>il17rel</i>	Interleukin-17 receptor E	Activation of signaling pathways resulting in expression and production of inflammatory cytokines	T-helper 17 cells	GGTGTCTCAGGGCCTTCACT, AGTTGTGAGGGGAGGCAAAAGT	114550154	147
<i>il21r</i>	Interleukin-21 receptor	Proliferation and differentiation of lymphocytes	T, B and NK cells	TATCACAGGTGTGGACCATGATT, GCTACTGGCTCACITTCACAAG	114547911	129
<i>il22ra2</i>	Interleukin-22 receptor subunit alpha 2	Binding to and inhibition of interleukin-22 activity	Dendritic cells, epithelial cells	CAACAGCATCCTCTGACAGTTG, GGCCAGCCAATCAGGAGCA	114572444	151
Further immune genes:						
<i>map3k7</i>	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase 7, also known as TAK1	Cellular responses to environmental challenges	Host cells	CTTTAGTGTGAGTCCGACAG, GTTTTCAGTGTCCAGGGCG	114573089	203
<i>mark3</i>	Microtubule affinity-regulating kinase 3	Intracellular signaling	Host cells	GGAAAGTCACAGTCTCACAGT, AACTGGCCGACACATCTCTCA	114546320	179
<i>mmp9</i>	Matrix metalloproteinase 9	Degradation of extracellular matrix; activation of interleukin-1 β , and cleavage of several chemokines	Neutrophilic granulocytes, macrophages, and fibroblasts	GTCTGTGACACCGCTGTAATTG, AGATGGCAAGTTGTGGTGACG	114558244	127
<i>mmp13b</i>	Matrix metalloproteinase 13, isoform beta	Tissue remodeling and repair; angiogenesis	Cells of smooth muscle tissue, respiratory epithelial cells	CATATTTAGTGGGATCCAGATGTG, ACACCGGAAAACCTCTGCT	114552539	147
<i>s100a1</i>	S100 calcium-binding protein A1	Regulation of cell cycle progression and differentiation; stimulation of Ca ²⁺ release, inhibition of microtubule assembly	Cardiac and skeletal muscle cells	CCTAGCAGCCAGCAAGGACC, GGTGAAGTGGACTTCAGGAG	114557017	88
<i>uchl1</i>	Ubiquitin carboxy-terminal hydrolase L1	Degradation of proteins	Various tissues and organs, mainly in the nervous system and endocrine tissues	GAACAAGATGATGAGC, GTTTCGGGACGGCGGACAGT	114568703	95
<i>fth1b</i>	Ferritin heavy polypeptide 1b	Intracellular iron storage	Macrophages and oligodendrocytes	ACCAGAAATGAGTTCGCAAATCC, GATAAACATAAGAGGCATAGAGCT	115586070	101
<i>lyg</i>	Lysozyme g	Defense against bacterial infection	Myeloid lineage cells	AAGGAGGGATAGCAGCTACAA, GCAACAACATCATTGGAGTAGTC	120556530	103

Table 2

The top 20 boldest individuals identified in this study.

Top 20 BI	Individual fish code	Activity [cm]	Latency closest approach [s]	Closest distance [cm]	Number of approaches
1 X	7018	21.7	1	≤10	1
2 X	7413	19.9	1	≤10	1
3 X	7366	17.7	4	≤10	3
4 X	7522	6.1	4	≤10	3
5 Y	0464	55.5	1	≤10	1
6 Y	0100	3.5	1	≤5	1
7 X	7173	4.6	1	≤5	1
8 Y	7240	22.2	1	≤10	1
9 X	7674	20.4	1	≤5	1
10 X	7246	13.4	1	≤10	1
11 Y	0495	11.2	1	≤5	1
12 Y	8594	12.5	4	≤10	5
13 Y	7481	26.3	1	≤5	1
14 X	8752	13.7	9	≤10	2
15 X	0461	8.1	1	≤10	1
16 X	7536	2.4	1	≤10	2
17 Y	7074	3.2	2	≤5	1
18 Y	0410	3.1	1	≤10	1
19 Y	1386	5.3	1	≤10	1
20 Z	0063	7.8	6	≤10	8

X-female, Y-male, Z-individuals with indeterminate gonads.

osmolality, and activities of the metabolic enzymes ALT, AST, LDH, and ALP were unchanged ($p \geq 0.05$) after the crowding challenge, either within a group or between groups, when compared to unstressed controls (Table 3). Remarkably, the cortisol levels between the bold and shy groups were statistically different, except for the levels determined at 24 h after the challenge. The cortisol level, on average, was about 5 times higher in the control SI group than in the corresponding BI group. The highest value of 669.4 nmol cortisol per L plasma was recorded in the SI group at 30 min after the challenge, and this value was 2.5-fold higher than the corresponding value in the BI group ($p < 0.05$). Also, at 30 min and 12 h after the challenge, the plasma cortisol levels were 2-fold higher in the SI than in the BI group ($p < 0.05$).

3.3. Assessment of the immune competence of bold versus shy personalities

The injection of 5×10^7 inactivated *A. hydrophila* into the peritoneal cavity had no significant impact on the body weights or somatic indices of either the bold or the shy European perch (Table 4). However, we detected significantly different expression profiles in the head kidneys and peritoneal cells when we compared the BI and SI. We established primer assays for 47 immune-related genes to profile their expression levels at 1, 3, and 7 days after stimulation with *A. hydrophila* (Table 1, Fig. 2). Our immunological qPCR assays were at detectable levels across all samples investigated, except for *il12b* and *il24*.

Table 3Physiological parameters (mean \pm SEM) recorded in European perch after crowding challenge.

	ALT [ukat/L]	AST [ukat/L]	LDH [ukat/L]	ALP [ukat/L]	Glucose [mmol/L]	Cortisol [nmol/L]	Osmolyte [mmol/kg]
Bold group (n = 5)							
CTRL	0.31 \pm 0.18	3.02 \pm 2.27	6.82 \pm 4.16	0.64 \pm 0.38	4.98 \pm 1.10	54.40 \pm 59.67 ^A	220.00 \pm 126.90
30 min	0.39 \pm 0.33	1.85 \pm 1.07	9.45 \pm 10.29	0.41 \pm 0.28	10.72 \pm 6.99	266.80 \pm 272.65 ^A	119.80 \pm 148.25
12 h	0.22 \pm 0.08	3.43 \pm 2.16	16.23 \pm 8.27	0.29 \pm 0.09	5.60 \pm 1.35	357.50 \pm 164.69 ^A	265.40 \pm 133.62
24 h	0.55 \pm 0.09	5.61 \pm 3.34	34.57 \pm 29.82	0.82 \pm 0.52	4.52 \pm 2.37	273.74 \pm 142.62	334.60 \pm 11.64
Shy group (n = 5)							
CTRL	0.46 \pm 0.38	4.86 \pm 4.20	12.55 \pm 10.66	0.18 \pm 0.15	4.16 \pm 2.38	277.20 \pm 176.94 ^B	205.60 \pm 153.70
30 min	0.39 \pm 0.33	6.37 \pm 5.15	31.06 \pm 17.00	0.41 \pm 0.19	8.98 \pm 4.25	669.40 \pm 146.93 ^B	198.40 \pm 162.06
12 h	0.56 \pm 0.03	3.25 \pm 2.64	16.16 \pm 11.06	0.50 \pm 0.29	7.02 \pm 1.04	524.80 \pm 128.00 ^B	334.80 \pm 20.62
24 h	0.41 \pm 0.01	1.99 \pm 1.44	12.71 \pm 8.57	0.37 \pm 0.12	6.04 \pm 2.47	284.40 \pm 194.46	339.80 \pm 15.73

CTRL - control; ALT - Alanine aminotransferase; AST - Aspartate aminotransferase; LDH - Lactate dehydrogenase; ALP - Alkaline phosphatase. ^{A, B} Different letters within a row indicate a significant difference between groups with $p \leq 0.05$.

In the head kidneys of both BI and SI, the levels of *mmp9* were increased on day 1 and then consistently decreased on days 3 and 7 after injection compared to PBS-injected control fish ($p \leq 0.03$) (Fig. 2). In addition, *saa5* levels were commonly elevated ($p < 0.03$) in BI and SI compared to controls on day 1 after bacterial injection. At the same time point, the transcript levels of seven immune genes (*tlr2*, *ighm*, *il17rel*, *il1b*, *il6*, *il6ra*, and *serpine1*) were significantly increased ($p < 0.04$) in the BI group, while six immune genes (*cd8a*, *timd4*, *il15*, *il6rb*, *il7r*, and *tnf*) were significantly decreased ($p < 0.03$) in the SI compared to the control values. At day 3 after injection, the levels of six immune genes (*il17a*, *il2rb*, *il6ra/b*, *map3k7*, as well as *mmp9*) were commonly reduced ($p \leq 0.03$) in the BI and SI groups compared to controls, while *cd4* levels were induced in the BI (with $p = 0.03$) but reduced in the SI ($p = 0.02$). Four additional genes were reduced ($p \leq 0.04$) in expression in the BI group (*cd209*, *il17f*, *il1b*, and *il22ra2*) and SI group (*il7r*, *itga2*, *tgfbr*, and *tnf*) compared to controls at day 3 after injection. Levels of *tgfbr* (as well as *mmp9*) were significantly induced in the BI group ($p = 0.01$), but reduced in the SI ($p = 0.04$) at day 7 after injection. At the same time point, two differentially expressed genes were found in the BI group (induced: *ccl20* and *itga2*) and five in the SI group (induced: *cd8a*, *timd4*, and *kldr1*; reduced: *il6rb* and *serpine1*) ($p < 0.05$).

In the peritoneal cells of both the BI and SI groups, the levels of 15 immune genes (*ccl20*, *cd4*, *cd68*, *cd8a*, *cd8b*, *cd74*, *ighm*, *il17a*, *il17f*, *il2rb*, *il6rb*, *il17r*, *il4i1*, *kldr1*, and *lyg*) were commonly reduced ($p < 0.05$), while only two genes (*il10* and *serpine1*) were induced ($p \leq 0.01$) compared to controls at day 1 after bacterial injection. At the same time point, the transcript level of one gene (*il22ra2*) was increased and the levels of two genes (*map3k7* and *uchl*) were decreased in the BI group compared to the control values ($p \leq 0.04$), while in the SI group, two immune genes (*ifng* and *tnf*) were increased and six genes (*ccl25*, *tlr2*, *timd4*, *il15*, *il17rel*, and *il21r*) were decreased compared to control values ($p \leq 0.04$).

Three and seven days after injection, the levels of two immune genes in the BI group (*ight* and *kldr1*) or three immune genes in the SI group (*il17rel*, *timd4*, and *serpine1*) were reduced compared to the controls ($p < 0.04$). In addition, at day 3 after injection, twelve genes (increased: *il17a*, *il17f*, and *mark3*; decreased: *c3*, *tlr2*, *cd209*, *il17rel*, *il2rb*, *il6*, *il6ra*, *serpine1*, and *uchl*) were differentially expressed in the BI group compared to the controls ($p < 0.04$), while only two genes (increased: *il7r*; decreased: *cd4*) were differentially expressed in the SI group compared to the controls ($p < 0.04$). At day 7 after injection, the levels of three genes (*cxcl8*, *cd209*, *mmp9*) were decreased in the BI group ($p < 0.05$), while one gene (*ighm*) was induced in the SI group ($p = 0.045$).

Having validated a proper transcriptional response of the immune system to the bacterial stimulus (compared to the unstimulated controls), we then focused on the statistical differences in immune gene expression between bold and shy perch. In the head kidney, the *cc125* transcript levels were increased by 1.2- to 1.3-fold ($q < 0.003$) in the BI versus SI groups at days 1 and 7 after stimulation, as well as in the

Table 4

Body weight and somatic indices (mean \pm SEM) of European perch after *A. hydrophila* injection.

	Weight [g]	Sex	HSI	GSI	PVSI	SSI	CSI
Bold group (n = 5 per group)							
CTRL	66.00 \pm 1.14	4X/ 1Y	1.86 \pm 0.49	2.56 \pm 1.96	2.96 \pm 0.95	0.08 \pm 0.01	0.14 \pm 0.01
1 dpi	69.20 \pm 5.85	3X/ 2Y	2.00 \pm 0.64	1.76 \pm 1.78	3.49 \pm 0.96	0.06 \pm 0.02	0.12 \pm 0.01
3 dpi	69.60 \pm 4.56	2X/ 3Y	2.05 \pm 0.75	3.44 \pm 2.25	3.23 \pm 1.96	0.08 \pm 0.03	0.15 \pm 0.03
7 dpi	60.80 \pm 4.21	1X/ 3Y/ 1Z	1.88 \pm 0.47	3.11 \pm 2.01	2.86 \pm 0.28	0.08 \pm 0.03	0.12 \pm 0.01
Shy group (n = 5 per group)							
CTRL	65.20 \pm 4.44	1X/ 4Y	2.22 \pm 0.31	2.71 \pm 2.17	3.36 \pm 1.22	0.07 \pm 0.01	0.13 \pm 0.02
1 dpi	71.80 \pm 9.09	4X/ 1Y	1.85 \pm 0.57	1.00 \pm 1.03	3.34 \pm 0.35	0.08 \pm 0.03	0.13 \pm 0.01
3 dpi	70.80 \pm 5.93	1X/ 4Y	1.97 \pm 1.38	2.99 \pm 2.56	3.65 \pm 0.84	0.11 \pm 0.05	0.17 \pm 0.04
7 dpi	57.40 \pm 3.29	2X/ 3Y	1.55 \pm 0.72	2.95 \pm 2.05	2.53 \pm 0.75	0.09 \pm 0.05	0.14 \pm 0.04

CTRL – control (7 days post-injection [dpi]); HSI - hepatosomatic index; GSI - gonadosomatic index; PVSI - perivisceral fat index; SSI - splenosomatic index; CSI - cardiosomatic index. X-female, Y-male, Z-individuals with indeterminate gonads.

control BI versus control SI groups (Fig. 3). *Ighm* was increased by 1.2- to 1.4-fold ($q < 0.006$) in the head kidney of the BI versus SI groups at days 1 and 3 after stimulation as well as in the control BI versus control SI groups. *Cd74* was increased by 1.3- to 1.5-fold ($q < 0.0001$) in the head kidney and peritoneal cells of the BI versus SI groups at 1 d after stimulation, as well as in the peritoneal cells of the control BI versus control SI groups (1.2-fold; $q = 0.02$). More pronounced expression differences were evident in the peritoneal cells of the BI versus SI groups for *ighm* (increased by 2.2-fold; $q < 0.0001$) and *c3* (decreased by 36.7-fold; $q = 0.03$) in unstimulated fish and for *mmp9* at day 3 after stimulation (decreased by 5.1-fold; $q = 0.01$).

Ingenuity bioinformatic analyses predicted the transcription factors that were most likely relevant for the observed expression patterns in the head kidney of challenged BI and SI. These factors comprised the typical *nf-kb/rel*, *stat*, and *irf* family members (and their associated regulators), in addition to other transcriptional activators (Fig. 4). Although the transcription factor networks appear quite heterogeneous at first glance, common and opposing upstream patterns are evident for the BI and SI. Most likely, *stat3* was activated 3 d after stimulation in both the BI and SI groups (Fig. 4B, E), but it caused the differential expression of various immune genes in cooperation with the other regulatory factors. The canonical inhibitors of *nf-kb/rel* (*nfkbia* or *nfkib*) were activated 3 d after stimulation in the BI group, but were suppressed in the SI group. At the same time, *irf3* was suppressed in the BI group, but activated in the SI group. Altogether, the upstream regulatory networks suggest that the heterogeneous set of differentially modulated transcriptional factors is presumably reflected by the distinct responses to bacterial stimulation in the BI versus SI group.

3.4. Phagocytosis of latex beads

The fluorescent-labeled latex beads were used to simulate a pathogen-host interaction in infected European perch to study the potential of leukocytes to ingest the latex beads (Fig. 5, Table 5) and provoke proinflammatory processes. The percentage of uptake of the latex beads was statistically higher for lymphoid head-kidney cells than for myeloid head-kidney cells in both the BI and SI groups (Table 5). The phagocytic capacity of either the myeloid or lymphoid cells was not

statistically different between the BI and SI for 1, 2, or 3 or more beads. In general, the phagocytotic capacity of myeloid and lymphoid cells was by far the highest for the ingestion of one latex bead, while the phagocytic capacity for 2 or 3 or more beads was 2/3 times lower than for 1 bead in both cell groups.

4. Discussion

The exploration of animal personality has been expanding from mammals to fish for several years. Personality is assumed to shape reproduction and survival while also increasing disease resistance and stress tolerance ([9,17], and references therein). A general conception is that, among mammalian and non-mammalian animals, less fearful and proactive individuals with bold personalities tend to resume activity earlier than those with shy personalities, and that their activities (including feeding, attacking, and mating) are associated with better growth, elevated stress tolerance, and adequate immune strategies for survival (c.f. [23,24] for macaques [25,26]; for birds [27]; for lizards [28]; for mealworms). The consistency of these trait combinations and their correlation with bold-shy personalities has been documented both for domesticated and wild animal species, thereby allowing, at least partly, the assumption of a genetic basis for personality and its probable inheritance, and thus the potential for selection of those traits. Activity and higher explorative behavior are usually positively correlated with better appetite and an elevated growth rate, since proactive animals are more likely to tap into a larger food supply compared with reactive animals [29].

Our results affirm that juvenile European perch exhibit different personality types. The open-field and novel-object tests performed in the present study clearly discriminated between proactive individuals with pronounced exploration behavior and reactive individuals that took a freeze-hide position when faced with an unknown situation or object. These results are in line with findings for rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) [14] or European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) [30].

Previous studies have revealed that BI produce low levels of corticosteroid hormones, mostly cortisol, in response to distress [6,31,32]. Lower cortisol levels were found in bold common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) [33], bold mullet (*Argyrosomus japonicus*) [34], and bold Japanese flounder (*Paralichthys olivaceus*) [35] as well as in higher vertebrates, including bold rhesus macaques (*Macaca mulatta*) [36], bold mink (*Neogale vison*) [37] and bold great tits (*Parus major*) [38]. This finding is in line with our study, as bold perch had lower basal and crowding-induced cortisol concentrations, in contrast to the elevated cortisol levels across almost all matching SI groups (Table 3). The poorer ability of SI to cope with stress was already evident during the novel-object tests. Different cortisol concentrations between bold and shy personalities usually reflect particular defense strategies. Freeze-hide positions have been interpreted as the adaptive response to a particular threat [39], but the BI displayed a fight-flight position, since they are generally less fearful and demonstrate their social dominance [31]. By contrast, bold behavior is linked to aggressiveness, as documented for a wide range of animals (c.f. [40] for fish; [41] for birds; [42] for caviar). Aggressiveness is not among the desirable aquaculture traits, but the level of conspecific aggressiveness is particularly high under predation pressure. Even though predators can be eliminated in the hatchery-rearing environment, cannibalism remains an important factor in European perch culture [43]. The heritability ratio of aggressiveness is still controversial. For instance, in the zebrafish *Danio rerio*, the heritability of aggressiveness was estimated at 0.36, while it was 0.76 in the case of boldness [44], suggesting that aggressiveness may also be aroused by environmental influences, including feeding [45], stocking density [46,47], and predation pressure [40,48]. Therefore, aggressiveness could be minimized by an accordingly modified husbandry management protocol.

An exciting hypothesis arising from the research on personality is that temperament may modulate the immune response [49].

Fig. 2. Modulation of immune genes for the head kidney and peritoneal cells after injection of inactivated *Aeromonas hydrophila* into bold (BI) and shy (SI) European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*) (as indicated above the heatmap). The heatmap illustrates the fold-change values of the *A. hydrophila*-injected groups (at 1, 3, and 7 days post-injection; n = 5 per group) relative to the control (CTRL, set at 1.0; n = 5) for the immune genes listed on the right margin. Blue fields indicate downregulation, red indicate upregulation relative to the control value; only significant copy-number changes with p < 0.05 are indicated.

Fig. 3. Profile of selected genes differentially expressed in (A) head kidney and (B) peritoneal cells of bold (BI, red bars) versus shy European perch (SI, blue bars) at 1 d, 3 d, and 7 d after *A. hydrophila* injection parallel to PBS-injected controls. Bars represent the averaged copy numbers quantified in 10 ng preamplified reverse-transcribed RNA; dots represent the individual copy numbers; error bars represent the standard error of the mean. Asterisks denote significantly different transcript levels (*, q < 0.05; **, q < 0.01; ***, q < 0.001).

Presumably, the proactive and explorative bold fish have a higher probability of meeting different pathogens that will challenge and train their immune system and provoke the development of distinct defense strategies [12,50,51]. Additionally, BI and SI have different capacities to control their environment under distress conditions [6]. The

hypothalamic–pituitary–interrenal axis mediates the communication between the brain and the immune system of fish and might suppress immune responses of stressed SI in a more efficient way, thereby increasing their vulnerability to diseases [52–54]. This phenomenon has been reported for mammals, such as rhesus macaques (*M. mulatta*) [23],

Fig. 4. Interaction networks predicting potential upstream regulators that might be responsible for the expression patterns observed in the head kidney of bold individuals (BI) (A–C) and shy individuals (SI) (D–F) at the timepoints given above the schemes. The observed upregulation or downregulation of the differentially expressed genes (arranged in the outer circle) is marked according to the colors of the heatmap in Fig. 2. The upstream regulators (arranged in the inner circle) are highlighted in yellow or green to indicate their putative activation or inhibition, respectively. Uncertain states due to lack of knowledge are indicated by white symbols.

Fig. 5. Phagocytosis of latex beads by macrophages, 1 – without latex beads, 2 – with one latex bead, and 3 – with 3 and more latex beads. Phalloidin–tetramethylrhodamine B isothiocyanate was used for actin labeling. The scale bar represents 20 µm.

Table 5

The phagocytic capacity (mean ± SEM) of leukocytes isolated from the head kidney of European perch.

	Bold group (n = 3)	Shy group (n = 3)
Phagocytic capacity [%]		
<i>Fish weight [g]</i>	52.0 ± 3.0	49.33 ± 1.15
<i>Myeloid cells</i>	35.43 ± 4.91	40.80 ± 5.49
1 bead	57.77 ± 2.96 ^a	55.47 ± 6.64 ^a
2 beads	22.83 ± 2.36 ^b	19.53 ± 1.95 ^b
3 and more beads	18.97 ± 2.36 ^b	23.07 ± 3.83 ^b
<i>Lymphoid cells</i>	56.33 ± 4.52	52.27 ± 5.72
1 bead	65.97 ± 2.21 ^a	65.57 ± 0.33 ^a
2 beads	18.83 ± 0.46 ^b	18.27 ± 1.09 ^b
3 and more beads	14.13 ± 1.77 ^b	15.30 ± 0.65 ^b

^{a,b} Letters in the column denote significant differences within the group p ≤ 0.05.

domestic dog (*Canis familiaris*) [55], and a few fish species [13,17,56]. For instance, the bold gilthead sea bream (*Sparatus aurata*) responded more effectively to *Vibrio anguillarum* bacterin vaccination, as evident from higher antibody titers within one month after vaccination [56,57]. In our study, we did not find any influence of personality on phagocytic activity, a dominant function of the innate immune response (Table 5 and Fig. 5). We can only speculate that (some) early innate immune mechanisms (at 2 h incubation in our case) were not affected by personality; nevertheless, the relatively high level of basal cortisol in SI could have significantly affected the immune response and the energetic–metabolic machinery.

Our multiplex-gene expression profiling of the head kidney and peritoneal cells revealed that the BI and SI groups responded differently to the intraperitoneal injection of inactivated *A. hydrophila*. The detection of increased levels of characteristic immune-gene markers indicated an early enhanced proliferation of (*tlr2*-positive) phagocytes and (*ighm*-positive) B cells in the head kidney of the BI group, whereas proliferation of (*cd8a*- and *timd4*-positive) lymphocytes requiring typical cytokines and receptors (including *il15*, *il7r* and *il6rb*), was presumably attenuated

in the head kidney of the SI group in response to pathogenic injection. The induced expression of genes coding for inflammatory markers, such as cytokines (il1b, il6, or tnf) and their receptors (for il6 and il17), indicated a pronounced inflammatory response in the BI group, in contrast to the SI group. In the later course of the immune response, the expression patterns of certain markers indicated a parallel reduction of (cd209-positive) antigen-presenting cells and (cd4-positive) T cells, followed by rising numbers of (itga2-positive) thrombocytes in the head kidney of the bold fish. In the head kidney of the SI group, the number of (cd4-positive) T cells and (itga2-positive) thrombocytes dropped at first, followed by rising numbers of (cd8a-, *timd4*-, or *klrd1*-positive) lymphocytes. These differential numbers of leucocyte populations likely reflect not only modulated proliferation but also migratory dynamics. However, such immune-cell trafficking is only partly reflected by expression profiling of the peritoneal cells. The main observation here is that the proportion of (cd4-, *cd8a/b*-, *ighm*- or *klrd1*-positive) lymphocytes was drastically reduced early after the stimulation and was not compensated at a later time point. In addition, (cd68-positive) macrophages decreased in number despite the presence of inflammatory signals (*ifng* and *tnf*) in the peritoneal cells of the BI group.

In general, the expression differences between BI and SI after bacterial stimulation were not outstandingly high, except for the *mmp9* and *c3* genes, which revealed more than 5- and 36-fold expression differences, respectively. *Mmp9* encodes matrix metalloproteinase 9, which is able to degrade the extracellular matrix and therefore has an essential involvement in wound healing, tissue remodeling, and development [58]. *Mmp9* is substantially expressed by circulating neutrophilic granulocytes [59] and is considered an indicator of activated immune processes in fish [60–62]. In addition, *c3* has long been recognized as an informative indicator of inflammation in fish [63–65]. The *c3* gene codes for a central component of the complement system, which efficiently fights invading pathogens. Notably, glucocorticoids, including cortisol, have been documented to alter the levels of *MMP9* in mammals [66] and *C3* in mammals and fish [67,68]. The latter studies showed that elevated cortisol concentrations decreased *c3* expression in rainbow trout (*O. mykiss*) [67], which is in line with the severely decreased *c3* transcript levels observed in unstimulated SI, which were characterized by elevated cortisol levels in the present study.

In summary, our data suggest that the fish personality is interlinked with health and stress-coping styles. However, these interconnections are complex, and the mechanisms underlying these connections are still underexplored and should be a future line of work.

5. Conclusion

Distinct fish personalities for selective breeding can be a viable approach for producing a desirable stock [69]. The selection for boldness may result in faster fish growth rates and higher yields, as bold fish may be more likely to forage for food and compete for resources. However, an important point to consider is that selecting specific personalities may entail unintended consequences, particularly if it results in reduced genetic diversity within the breeding stock. This can increase the risk of inbreeding depression and reduce the ability of the stock to adapt to changing environmental conditions, including the emergence of new (or variants of) pathogens. Generally, the expression of personality traits depends on a variety of factors, including predation pressure, food availability, social condition, and social interactions, which complicate the prediction of the offspring's personality types. The potential trade-offs should be carefully considered to promote genetic diversity and the long-term viability of fish breeding stock.

Ethical approval and consent to participate

This study was performed in compliance with the terms of the Czech legislation (section 16 of Act No.246/1992 Coll., on protection of animals against cruelty, as amended by Act No. 77/2004 Coll.). Animal

experiments have been approved by the Ministry of Education, approval ID: MSMT-18301/2018-2.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

The data presented in this study are available in this manuscript and its supplementary materials and are available on request from the corresponding authors.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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